

A proposal for a framework to address news deserts in hybrid local media ecologies

Carlos Rodríguez Urra. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso (Chile)

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=ZzoK2P4AAAAJ&hl=es>

ABSTRACT:

This article proposes the Independence- and Network-Adjusted News Desert Framework (INAD) as an operational procedure for assessing news deserts in hybrid local and hyperlocal media ecosystems (traditional media, the web and platforms), moving beyond assessments based solely on the number of outlets. The INAD is based on a central assumption: media pluralism is not equivalent to the sum of brands or accounts present in a territory, but rather to the existence of effectively independent editorial decision-making centres. Consequently, a territory may feature multiple ‘news’ actors and still function as a news desert or at-risk area if (i) a large proportion of the content fails to meet minimum standards of journalistic practice (regularity and provision of critical information) and/or (ii) the content is organised under concentrated control structures (ownership, funding or editorial coordination), thereby reducing the actual number of voices.

The framework comprises two components. First, a validation and independence matrix (binary 0/1 coding) that classifies actors as media outlets, mappable news spaces or non-news actors, incorporating minimum thresholds (at least one weekly publication and the presence of critical information) and a transparency index based on traceability (About, contact details, registered address, team identification, integrity standards and municipal affiliation). Second, a relational layer that distinguishes control/ownership networks (clusters that shape effective plurality) from collaboration networks (reciprocal or unidirectional) that can increase resilience in peripheral territories without automatically implying a loss of independence.

As a demonstration, the INAD is applied to the Aysén Region (Chile), where media outlets are concentrated in Coyhaique and Puerto Aysén and distribution relies heavily on platforms (Facebook as an almost universal channel). The results reveal significant gaps between visibility and institutional traceability, as well as dynamics of inter-municipal and trans-regional collaboration. Overall, the INAD offers a replicable approach to moving from ‘presence maps’ to assessments of effective pluralism, incorporating platforms, transparency, dependency and networks as constituent dimensions of contemporary news deserts.

Keywords: news deserts; local and hyperlocal journalism; pluralism; transparency; media ownership; collaboration; digital platforms; Chile.

Introduction

Technological infrastructure and digital access, with a multitude of mobile devices facilitating a constant flow of information, have not fully resolved the challenge of ensuring access to relevant information across all regions in terms of local news coverage; this issue is compounded by concerns over the proliferation of fake or unverified news in a context where professionally verified information is required. In fact, recent research has identified a paradoxical phenomenon: whilst digital platforms proliferate, genuine ‘news deserts’ have emerged, corresponding to areas devoid of local media that guarantee geographically close and contextualised journalistic coverage (Abernathy, 2016; Gulyas, 2022; Rackaway, 2024).

Areas lacking formal media outlets are particularly vulnerable to the spread of disinformation and fake news, as citizens do not have access to reliable and contextualised news. In this regard, disinformation as a problem emerges within the context of the digitalisation of the public sphere (Broseta et al., 2023) and may be present on social media platforms (Pérez-Curiel & Stamate, 2024), where even Google’s algorithms “determine the news and disinformation” (Abernathy, 2020, p.90) in the dissemination of local media news if there is no prior fact-checking. Disinformation has been classified as a genuine persuasion technique that has spread in the digital sphere “where it is easier than ever to disseminate information or disinformation on a massive scale and with immediate effect” (Escoda & Pedrero-Esteban, 2021, p.69). Against this backdrop, the importance of having media outlets staffed by professional journalists is all the more crucial in a scenario such as the current one.

News deserts do not merely refer to the absence of media outlets; they also exist in local contexts where there is no editorial independence and where the media are under the control of local governments (Rodríguez-Urra et al., 2025). This interpretation is relevant for providing greater clarity when studying regions, insofar as, even in recent years, news deserts have typically been analysed solely in terms of the binary relationship of ‘there is/there is not’ (Wang, 2023, p.312) media.

Another factor that can negatively affect national media systems is media concentration. Whilst a media outlet may offer objective information that meets professional journalistic standards, it is essential that there be a plurality of perspectives. We take the Chilean case to illustrate this point, where 90% of the circulation of the Chilean press at the national level is under the control of the El Mercurio/COPESA media duopoly (Mellado and Scherman, 2020; Santander, 2013; Sapiezynska and Lagos-Lira, 2016). Both newspapers are “driven by the economic and political interests of right-wing political parties” (Sepúlveda, 2024, p.430), which impacts the diversity of sources, as evidenced by the invisibilisation of certain sectors (Sapiezynska, 2014).

These reflections are linked to the issue of news deserts, insofar as individuals may not be represented within newsrooms depending on the latter’s criteria. These warnings are linked to the observations of international organisations such as UNESCO (2005, 2017), which

have argued that media concentration and the lack of diversity of voices constitute a direct threat to the right to freedom of expression, particularly in areas neglected by the information market.

Indeed, media concentration is linked to concerns regarding “media diversity as the foundation of democracy and the quality of media content” (Noam, 2009, p.35), precarious working conditions (Suenzo et al., 2020) and the role of the State (Guerra, 2019; Australian Competition & Consumer Commission, 2019). These factors have a direct impact on pluralism, understood as a principle that seeks to create “technical conditions for a diverse range of offerings (to) ensure equal access to content, including online content” (Bayer, 2019, p.130). This discussion engages with the contributions of authors such as Karppinen (2013), who posits that the media “will never be completely independent of other powerful influences, such as pressure from governments, interest groups and media owners, and therefore media power will always be strategically used to influence agendas and the framing of public issues” (p.61).

Another area of analysis involves identifying the presence of public media. These form an important part of media systems (Neff & Pickard, 2021), whilst “the characteristics and values of public media underpin well-informed democratic societies” (Warner, 2019, p. 3). Other researchers, such as De Moraes (2011), point out that a clear distinction must be made between public and state media, noting that state media correspond to “spaces of cohesion of purpose and consensus” (De Moraes, 2011, p.48), whereas the public sphere “is plural, heterogeneous, diverse and conflictual, just like society” (Martín-Barbero, 2008, p.10). In this way, public media succeed in representing plurality.

In this context, this article proposes the Independence- and Network-Adjusted News Desert Framework (INAD) as an operational procedure for assessing news deserts beyond a simple count of media outlets. The INAD integrates (i) a minimum threshold for journalistic operation—including a frequency of at least one weekly publication and the presence of critical reporting—, (ii) variables of transparency, ownership and structural dependence (including municipal dependence), and (iii) a relational layer that distinguishes control/ownership networks from collaborative networks. As a result, the framework allows us to estimate not only the ‘presence’ of media in a territory, but also the effective plurality of editorial decision-making centres, and to distinguish between territories that are ‘covered’, ‘at risk’ or ‘deserted’ using replicable criteria.

2. Literature & Theoretical Anchors

The concept of the ‘news desert’ has been interpreted in various ways, reflecting its development in recent years based on academic discourse around the world. Gulyas (2023) identifies a sustained growth in scientific research, but points to structural limitations such as the “lack of agreed definitions. Interpretations of ‘local media’ or ‘news desert’ vary significantly” (p.286). In a previous study, the British researcher herself (2022) summarises the research field as “the comparison of the availability, access or use of local news or media between different localities and/or over time” (p.18). These definitions have

enabled the development of measurement frameworks, but have also reinforced a bias towards approaches centred on media supply and presence, raising questions about effective pluralism and editorial independence.

Abernathy's studies (2016; 2018; 2020) in the United States have been pioneering and articulate the link between the local news ecology and democracy. In her latest report from 2020, the author defines the issue as areas comprising "rural or urban communities with limited access to the kind of credible and comprehensive news and information that nourishes democracy at its most fundamental level (grassroots)" (Abernathy, 2020, p.18). From her earliest work, the discussion has been linked to industrial transformations and shifts in ownership: the loss of local newspapers led to increased media concentration driven by the emergence of new press barons, against a backdrop that "coincides with a period of enormous upheaval and concern for the entire journalism industry" (Abernathy, 2016, p.6) against the backdrop of digitalisation and the expansion of social media. Later, Abernathy argued that "almost one in five newspapers has disappeared, and many others have become 'ghosts' of their former selves" (Abernathy, 2018, p.5) in his country. Taken together, these contributions have consolidated a view that links the availability of local news to democratic capacities for oversight and deliberation, which are not being met as a result of the decline of the traditional press.

Other contributions have characterised news deserts as communities no longer covered by daily newspapers in an environment marked by inequalities (Owilla et al., 2020), or as municipalities without local media or without journalistic coverage of local issues (Jerónimo et al., 2022). Despite the diversity of approaches, there is a shared core: the central role of space and geography, given that "the concept of space or geography as a crucial role in local journalism and newspapers" (Wang, 2023, p.305), whilst today, geography is a tool increasingly used in journalism and communication studies (Sousa, 2025). In line with this, Karlsson and Rowe (2019) note that "the connection between geography and news production has previously been highlighted within journalism studies" (p.19). This spatial emphasis allows for the study of territorial inequalities, but also requires more refined indicators to distinguish between the nominal presence of media outlets and meaningful local coverage. Some national studies that have used cartography as a visual tool to highlight media deficits in different regions include those by Fundación Gabo (2026) and FOPEA (2021), amongst others.

At the same time, related concepts have emerged that emphasise aspects of access and infrastructure. For example, Gulyas and Baines (2020) propose considering 'local media gaps' linked to the population's lack of access to information sources, which does not necessarily correspond to a lack of media outlets. Complementarily, Ferrier (2016) spoke of 'media deserts' to gauge shortcomings based on technical infrastructure and its absence, including a lack of connectivity. This line of thinking reinforces the structural component of the problem, but at the same time raises a tension: what happens when the circulation of information does exist on platforms, albeit not under professional standards or with no accountability?

Ramos (2023) notes that "social media may have become a major provider of local information" (p.12), in contexts where "local communities report and discuss information relevant to the community" (Spasov et al., 2024, p.28). Whilst these platforms succeed in

diversifying information and reach within media systems, the methodological challenge lies precisely in determining when such spaces can be considered valid “media” or “informational actors”. Researchers note that platforms such as Facebook “are not impartial or objective sources of news and information” (Freeman, 2020, p.536). Here, the focus on hybrid media systems and platform governance becomes central, insofar as algorithmic intermediation, visibility, monetisation and the architecture of participation condition both production and circulation, rendering insufficient any assessment that merely identifies the presence of content without examining transparency, editorial responsibility and dependence on networks. A key aspect lies in the provision of critical information to communities regarding current affairs related to emergencies and public safety, education, health, traffic conditions and road status, the environment and planning (Conte, 2022), as well as political content for public deliberation, as these are essential.

Political information must differ from that which is classified as propaganda, as the latter fails to comply with the journalistic principle of impartiality and does not contribute to the construction of public spheres characterised by a plurality of perspectives. A specific case has been the media system in Hungary until Viktor Orbán’s defeat, whilst researchers such as Polyák and Urbán (2024) indicate that the country has experienced extensive news deserts as a result of the ruling party’s influence over almost all media, leading to a situation where “freedom and diversity of information are severely limited. In the case of local media, the dominance of a single party means that readers have very limited access to independent information on issues of local relevance” (p.89). Here, Abel (2022) had identified the existence of few Hungarian cities with a political opposition, and it was these that were becoming news deserts due to the lack of independent news.

In this discussion, it is crucial to emphasise that hyperlocal journalism is not limited to the ‘local’ in the broadest sense, but rather strongly encompasses the hyperlocal level, where the role of news is played out in micro-territories and specific communities. Rodríguez-Urra et al. (2024) have explored the links between hyperlocal journalism and news deserts in local journalism, highlighting challenges in audience engagement, citizen journalism, and business models. Likewise, academia has increasingly begun to highlight the existence of community-based media such as hyperlocal outlets, which are attracting attention “among digital initiatives, renewing the link with the community” (Vázquez-Herrero et al., 2023, p.8). This shift can be interpreted as a paradigm shift if we consider that, for example, in Brazil these media outlets—despite their importance in regional media systems—have rarely been recognised in a manner commensurate with their contribution (DeMendonça & Brito-Batista, 2021).

In the hyperlocal sphere, this reality becomes urgent. Toomer (2024) observes that commercial and independent hyperlocal sites tend to emerge more easily in relatively prosperous areas, whereas in contexts “where the market fails in terms of advertising, sites find it much harder to thrive and their existence is precarious” (p.57), increasing the risk of information gaps and, consequently, of news deserts. In this context, Nygren (2018) argues that hyperlocal digital media can bridge the information gap left by the decline of the traditional press in a scenario of economic transformation (p.45). There are also examples of freelancer collaboration in Latin America (Mesquita, 2023) and institutional collaboration, such as the British case of partnerships between the BBC and regional and hyperlocal media for collaboration and content sharing (Marsden, 2017).

Other authors, such as Gulyas (2022), indicate that the press sector has also experienced disruption since the introduction of new formats and new channels for the distribution of local news (such as hyperlocal outlets and community groups on social media platforms). Although the current landscape is turbulent, “consumption of local news remains relatively high in the UK at a national level. Whilst the readership of print newspapers has declined, the consumption of local news online has expanded significantly” (Gulyas, 2022, p.21).

However, these developments coexist with structural limitations: small digital-native media outlets may lack robust audience metrics, which may mean that “local authorities are not interested in appearing” (Smyrnaioi et al., 2015, p.176) in them. Furthermore, hyperlocal media face fundamental constraints, such as low population density or distribution costs that are difficult for small organisations to sustain (Downman & Murray, 2020). From the perspective of the information ecosystem, the relationship between hyperlocality and disinformation is also ambivalent: Turner and Harte (2022) describe emotional ties to hyperlocal sites and deliberative spaces, but warn that this “leaves them more exposed to disinformation (...) audiences are not necessarily equipped to scrutinise the content” (p.53).

Jerónimo (2024) points out that content can go viral without prior scrutiny, which leads to the problem of disinformation and, on the other hand, to the tremendous challenge faced by newsrooms worldwide, which must earn and retain public trust through quality journalism—a challenge that is “greater in the case of local media, which are often less prepared” (p.9). The focus on hyperlocal areas is also underpinned by Rodgers’ (201) observation, where he discusses “a phenomenological duality. On the one hand, as activities rooted in place, taking place in situated environments. But, on the other hand, as inhabited spaces: geographically dispersed worlds that are both social and technical” (p.857). In short, the absence or weakness of the hyperlocal not only affects local coverage but can also amplify informational vulnerabilities: following the COVID-19 crisis, the hyperlocal retreat intensified and reconfigured ecosystems (Damanhoury et al., 2022), in line with the warning that communities abandoned by journalism and dominated by social media “are more vulnerable to disinformation as they rely on platform algorithms and social media administrators to moderate freedom of expression” (Steensen, 2023, p.416).

Another key factor in understanding the fragility of local journalism relates to the conditions under which journalists work, including attacks and threats against the press. In Europe, research has examined how these dynamics can discourage journalistic practice (Verza et al., 2024). Taking a broader view, “they have increased worldwide in recent years, as part of the decline in public trust in news and the media” (Nelson, 2021, p.105). In certain parts of Latin America, threats and coercive actions are reported with particular frequency (Fundación Gabo, 2022; Cadena & Zoeller, 2021; Harlow et al., 2022), which further complicates the sustainability of local media.

Overall, the literature confirms the value of the concept of news deserts, but also highlights a persistent limitation: count-based assessments tend to underestimate structural independence (ownership, funding and editorial dependence), the validity of which actors ‘count’ as media in platform environments (as opposed to ‘information spaces’ without minimum standards), and the network relationships that may concentrate editorial control or, conversely, strengthen capabilities through collaboration. This gap connects with the

political economy of communication and with the literature on media capture, insofar as dependence on funding/patronage and the concentration of control reduce effective plurality even when multiple brands exist. Building on these limitations, this article proposes the INAD as an operational procedure with decision rules and replicable indicators to classify news actors, measure independence, and refine the territorial diagnosis of news deserts in hybrid media ecosystems.

Methodology

The Independence- and Network-Adjusted News Desert Framework (INAD) is proposed as an operational procedure for assessing news deserts in hybrid local and hyperlocal media ecosystems (web + social media platforms + traditional media), moving beyond assessments based solely on counting media ‘presence’. This serves as a complement to the approach taken by Gulyas (2022)

The INAD is based on a central assumption: media plurality does not equate to the sum of brands or accounts existing in a territory, but rather to the existence of effectively independent editorial decision-making centres. Consequently, a territory may have multiple “news” actors and still function as a desert or risk area if a large part of that offering fails to meet minimum standards of journalistic practice (e.g., irregularity, opacity, lack of editorial accountability) or if the offering is organised under concentrated control structures (ownership, funding or editorial coordination), thereby reducing the actual number of voices.

Based on these two layers, the INAD provides three main outputs that complement the identification of media presence: (1) a classification of actors (media outlet vs. unvalidated ‘news space’) and their compliance with minimum standards; (2) a territorial diagnosis of media deserts/at-risk areas based on effective plurality (clusters) and structural dependence; and (3) a network map that distinguishes between concentration (control) and resilience (collaboration), useful for comparative research and for discussing interventions (public policy, funding, partnerships).

Operationalisation

4.1. Unit of analysis, territory and time frame

Once all spaces—virtual as well as conventional, sub-national, local or hyperlocal—have been identified through database searches or systematic methods, each type of media outlet is assigned a unit of analysis to determine its degree of independence.

The unit of analysis is the local/hyperlocal news actor: an entity that publishes information of public interest linked to a defined territory via the web, radio/TV or platforms. Coding is carried out within a standard observation window covering content produced during a current week. This can be done through a manual search, or by using extensions such as the Wayback Machine or another Google add-on. Given that the Chilean case may undergo temporary reconfigurations due to natural disasters (floods, earthquakes, major wildfires, etc.), it is recommended to incorporate a sampling strategy that reduces bias, as there may

be a prominence of information from local authorities; this can be achieved by switching to another week prior to any event of public impact.

4.2. INAD Matrix: variables, coding and evidence

The matrix organises variables into four blocks: local production and supply; transparency and accountability; ownership/funding and dependence; and networks.

Block A — Transparency and accountability (replicable indicators)

Here, the aim is to determine whether the organisation meets minimum traceability standards: who reports, how corrections are made, how to contact them, how artificial intelligence is used, what the organisation's vision and mission are, and what its registered address is. To this end, using a binary classification (0 = no, 1 = yes), media outlets must be assessed according to the following criteria:

- Existence of an 'About' section on the website or social media platform
- Existence of a presentation of the management team and journalists
- Transparency regarding the legal or tax address
- Existence of verifiable contact details (telephone or email)
- Existence of policies on correction or the use of artificial intelligence

Block B — Ownership, funding and structural dependence

Variables are coded to capture independence or subordination:

- Declared ownership / signs of control (qualitative record and, where possible, binary based on the presence/absence of verifiable evidence).

4.3. Network layer: construction of links and clusters

Network 1 — Control/ownership (concentration). A control link (edge) between two actors is defined when there is evidence of shared control or editorial coordination (e.g., common ownership or governance; belonging to a media group; sustained editorial coordination). The result is modelled as clusters of control, and the key indicator of territorial plurality shifts from the number of media outlets to the number of clusters (independent voices).

Network 2 — Collaboration (resilience). A collaboration link is defined when there is evidence of cooperation between actors without shared control (co-publication with credit, exchange of coverage, distribution, correspondent networks, training). Collaboration is interpreted as the capacity to expand coverage and sustain news provision in peripheral territories, without this automatically implying a loss of independence. Here, it is necessary

to specify whether the collaboration is permanent or sporadic. To address this detail, it is necessary to review media histories, groups formed between media outlets, and the traceability of author or journalist bylines in reports. In turn, to complement this section, interviews with the media must be conducted to learn more about this aspect.

Application

We will use the practical example of the scientific article by Rodríguez-Urra (2025) to apply this new matrix.

Gulyas (2022), in studying the methodological approaches to news deserts in the literature of the Global North, identifies four approaches for studying news deserts. We will briefly refer to each one (p.19):

- **Outlet focused:** centred on variations between different localities in the availability of local media, usually within a national framework. The aim is thus to study media concentration by examining historical and social contexts, as well as the political significance of the media in democratic contexts. The methodology involves creating projects that use datasets on the availability of local media in specific geographical units (municipalities, postcode areas), to which a map-based analysis is applied to reflect spatial inequalities in the provision of local news. The projects are not directly comparable with one another, as the level of detail varies in terms of their scope and the geographical units used.
- **Content-focused:** explores variations in how well communities are served in terms of local news availability and the robustness of local journalism. Its primary research method is content analysis, and although the approach is comparative given the depth of the analysis, this exercise is not carried out at a national scale.
- **Media ecology focused:** researchers examine either a large or limited number of small media ecosystems, but with a high capacity to capture detail by combining qualitative and quantitative methods. Here, they examine not only media-related factors but also various socio-economic factors. The approach is based on a sub-national scale, allowing for comparison between communities within the selected geographical areas.
- **Case study-focused:** this approach provides in-depth analysis of selected territorial units, which may be a village or a town, typically using qualitative methods. This approach aims to examine changes over time in the provision of local news in the selected locality and/or the impacts of these changes.

Whilst offering an overview of different interpretations, approaches and methods used, it is recognised that the study of news deserts can prove highly complex given the multitude of socio-economic aspects of a given area and the various parameters employed in research:

“I argue that research into spatial inequalities must go beyond merely recognising variations between different localities and seek to identify how and why the spatial context contributes to inequalities and is linked to existing socio-economic inequalities (...) Other challenges identified (...) include the compatibility between different studies on local media deserts, the distinction between large-scale and in-depth studies, variations in the spatial scales applied across different research projects, as well as in the definitions of local media” (Gulyas, 2022, p.25)

For Gulyas (2023), these approaches reflect not only different interpretations but also different methodologies and scales in the design of research into local media (p.286). Thus, news deserts constitute “a powerful concept that can speak to both academics and non-academic audiences” (Gulyas et al., 2023, p. 287).

In our case, in the study by Rodríguez-Urra (2025), we draw on the media ecology and content-focused approach proposed by Gulyas et al. (2023), in which we analyse the quantitative presence of media outlets by municipality across the region, as well as providing a brief overview of content creation by the identified media outlets to determine whether they are active or not. In view of this, the following categories were established as the preliminary focus of the INAD study:

- Low Risk: Assured pluralism, diverse formats, and a medium to high number of media outlets.
- Moderate Risk: Assured pluralism, but lacking format diversity, with a medium to high number of media outlets
- High Risk: Uncertain pluralism and minimal media diversity
- Desert: Non-existent pluralism and/or an extremely low number of media outlets

From a methodological perspective, the proposal is for an Independence- and Network-Adjusted News Desert Framework (INAD) comprising two integrated components. Firstly, a classification matrix is proposed for the identification and validation of local media actors, including platform-native actors present on social media. This will determine whether a given ‘news space’ should be considered a media outlet for news desert measurement. Secondly, a network layer is proposed that differentiates between (i) networks of ownership/control and (ii) networks of collaboration (capacity-building alliances that may mitigate news deserts without eliminating editorial plurality). The data presented in the following figures are hosted in the footer¹.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/20479828>

Figure 1: Mobile network 3G, 4 G y 5G. Source: Nperf .com (September 2023)

Before beginning the analysis, we should note that due to the remoteness of the region, the Aysén Region has few satellite and internet connection networks, as reflected in the screenshots obtained using the Nperf application in Figure 1. We can see that mobile connectivity is patchy across much of Chile, with the exception of the Aysén Region and areas further south. This is due to the remote nature of these areas and their lower population density.

Figure 2. Aysén región media system (Rodríguez-Urra et al-. 2025)

The media landscape of the Aysén region comprises a total of 63 media outlets, spread across 10 different municipalities. Most types of media are concentrated in the central municipalities of Aysén and Coyhaique. The former has 13 media outlets, whilst the latter, which is the regional capital, has 19. The remaining media outlets are distributed across the other municipalities, as shown in Figure 1.

In this illustration, we observe that the distribution is not uniform, with a mix of municipalities possessing independent media systems as well as a proliferation of municipal media. In specific cases such as O'Higgins and Guaitecas, there was a case of forced closure due to political differences. This has meant that the history of these territories has been affected in terms of pluralism. Furthermore, in the case of Chile Chico, we find that although there are six radio stations, two of them broadcast programming from regional groups and another two from municipal bodies, meaning that there is a moderate degree of independence.

Figure 3. Aysén región news deserts (Rodríguez-Urra et al-. 2025)

Taking into account the background information presented in Figure 1, this map covers the Aysén Region. Although media outlets are present across all areas, following the partial implementation of the INAD—which also reflects the results of previous research—it can be seen that there are areas designated as media deserts, as well as high-risk areas.

Following a review of databases, in the case of the Aysén Region, 63 catalogued media outlets are primarily concentrated in the cities of Coyhaique (the regional capital) and Puerto Aysén. Radio dominates the region (48 outlets) and is present in all communes, including remote areas with low population density. Radio stations account for 76% of the total, followed by digital-only outlets (10 outlets, 16%), four television channels (6%), and one print outlet (2%).

The analysis of media presence in the Aysén Region in Figure 2 shows that two out of ten municipalities (20%) are at low risk of being classified as news deserts, and these are located in the main cities. Additionally, 20% of the territory is at moderate risk, another 20% at high risk, and 40% can already be identified as a news desert. Lago Verde, Río

Ibáñez, Tortel, and O’Higgins are classified as news deserts² due to the presence of municipally administered radio stations. In high-risk cases, there is a slight increase in media outlets lacking diversity (Cochrane), and whilst there is a certain degree of balance between municipal and independent radio stations in Guaitecas, the situation in this commune has historically been precarious³, compounded by the absence of other types of media.

Figure 4. Platform presence across media system

If we consider 62 organisations (not 63, due to the recent closure of a media outlet in Guaitecas in 2023), 55 (88.7%) use Facebook, making it the ecosystem’s almost universal channel. In second place comes the website, with 43 out of 62 (69.4%), suggesting that a significant part of the system still maintains (or attempts to maintain) its own presence outside of platforms, albeit to a lesser extent than Facebook.

Further down the list are Instagram and X, both with 31 out of 62 (50.0%), as ‘intermediate’ adoption platforms: sufficiently present to form part of the regional news diet, but far from the ubiquity of Facebook. In fourth place is YouTube, with 26 out of 62 (41.9%), indicating selective use (likely associated with audiovisual formats or rebroadcasting strategies). Finally, TikTok remains at an early stage of adoption: only 8 out of 62 users (12.9%).

Key takeaway: the graph reflects a clear “pyramid”: Facebook at the top, the web as the second pillar, an intermediate Instagram/X block, and then YouTube and TikTok as more selective layers.

In municipalities with fewer actors, there is a trend towards single-channel use or dependence on a very small set of platforms. Given that there are 13 actors in Aysén, it

² In the southern municipalities, there has been a history of high volatility in ownership, subject to changes in local government, as well as informal and autonomous administrations, resulting in the intermittent functioning of local media.

³ Two decades ago, the former mayor of the municipality terminated the electricity supply to the Estrella del Mar radio station due to differences in ideological outlook. The case was subsequently referred to the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights (IACHR), which delivered a ruling in favour of the affected director of the radio station. See more at www.oas.org/es/cidh/decisiones/2016/CHPU12799ES.pdf

maintains a strong base on Facebook (92%), but shows a clear decline on the web (54%) and on Instagram/YouTube (38% each). TikTok is marginal (8%). This demonstrates that the flow of information is channelled mainly through Facebook. On the other hand, Cisnes has 8 media outlets, with Facebook and the web each accounting for 75%, Instagram 50%, and X/YouTube 25%. TikTok 13%. Another interesting case is Chile Chico (6 media channels, showing Facebook at 67%, X at 33%, TikTok at 33%, and Instagram/web at just 17% each; YouTube at 0%).

Figure 5. Transparency index

Figure 4 shows six areas identified by our framework. First, we have the presence of a contact form or contact details provided by the media outlet or news platform (Cont...), along with the ‘About’ section, which explains the purpose of the site or platform or what it is about. Next comes the legal address (legal), which indicates whether the media outlet discloses its location within the city or town. We also have the Team section/identification (Team S...), which lists the names and roles of the team members. Finally, we have whether the media outlet declares itself to be part of the administration of a municipal institution (Admini...) and whether there is any note regarding the integrity of the team (Team..., in yellow) in terms of the outlet’s stated principles and its role in society, as well as editorial policies and a code of ethics.

The transparency data show a consistent pattern: the most widespread dimension is Contact ($\approx 74\%$ of the regional total), followed by About ($\approx 53\%$) and Legal address ($\approx 48\%$). However, the indicators used to assess editorial accountability and institutional standards drop sharply: the Team section/identification reaches only $\approx 23\%$ and the Team integrity norm barely $\approx 6\%$. This gap suggests that a significant part of the ecosystem operates with visibility and contactability, but with low traceability regarding who makes editorial decisions and under what standards, reinforcing the need for minimum thresholds and transparency criteria in the INAD classification (media vs. news outlet). Furthermore, the distribution is geographically uneven: Coyhaique has the highest levels of transparency (Contact 100%, About 74%, Legal 63%, Team 47%, Team integrity norm 16%), whilst outlying municipalities show fragmented profiles or even total opacity (e.g., O’Higgins 0% across the observed indicators).

In intermediate municipalities, the asymmetry between ‘contactability’ and institutional traceability is repeated: in Aysén, for example, Contact reaches 92%, but the Team section drops to 15% and Team integrity norm is 0%, alongside Legal address at 38% and About at 54%. In Cisnes, the levels are more moderate (Contact 63%, About 50%, Legal 38%, Team 25%, Team integrity norm 0%). In small municipalities, extreme combinations

appear: Río Ibáñez has 100% for Contact but 0% for About/Team/Legal/Team integrity norm, whilst Lago Verde has 100% for About and 100% for Legal address, but 0% for Contact and 0% for Team integrity norm. These contrasts confirm that transparency is not a uniform feature of the ecosystem: there may be a public presence (and even legal formality) without clear mechanisms for editorial accountability, which is particularly relevant in ensuring that the availability of information is not confused with effective pluralism.

Figure 6. Information flows based on collaborative and proprietary networks. Source: own elaboration.

Following the interviews conducted in a previous study (Rodríguez-Urra et al., 2025), Figure 6 illustrates the collaboration nodes and information flows in relation to media ownership. Firstly, there is a network called MADIPRO, of which Radio Televisión Santa María is a part; this provides an inter-community link through its news programmes in Cochrane, Chile Chico, Puerto Aysén, Villa Mañihuales (in Puerto Aysén) and Cisnes. In turn, another interconnection is provided by Radio Ventisqueros, which has offices in Cochrane, Chile Chico and Cisnes. Furthermore, there is also a trans-regional network called “Radio Nahuel”, originating from the Los Lagos Region, which supplies some of its content to two radio stations located in the municipality of Aysén.

Following interviews with media representatives in Puerto Aysén, we have discovered that there are collaborative dynamics between local media outlets. Specifically, the media partners are Canal 11 TV and ComunicAysén, and Panorámica Informativa with Aysén TV. These collaborative arrangements arise due to the small teams working in these media outlets; whenever there is a news event or a journalistic piece needs to be produced in remote locations, the network springs into action. Similarly, one particular network links Radio Milenaria with radio stations in the coastal area of Cisnes and a station in Guaitecas, whilst sharing content related to public demonstrations and emergencies that may affect sea or land routes. Finally, another collaborative network exists between Aysén TV and RTV Santa María, though this is one-way due to the background of Aysén TV’s director and his friendship with Santa María. Something similar occurs with ComunicAysén and El Divisadero de Coyhaique, whilst the former acts as the newspaper’s correspondent office in Puerto Aysén.

Taken together, the map reveals an ecosystem in which Coyhaique functions as a central hub for inter-municipal connectivity, whilst several municipalities are integrated through one-way collaborations (asymmetrical flows towards media with greater amplification capacity) and reciprocal collaborations (sustained exchange between digital platforms and TV/radio). This configuration reinforces the need to distinguish, when diagnosing news deserts, between control/ownership networks and collaborative networks, as the latter can expand coverage and resilience without necessarily reducing editorial plurality.

Conclusions

This article has proposed the Independence- and Network-Adjusted News Desert Framework (INAD) as a methodological guide for assessing news deserts in hybrid local and hyperlocal media ecosystems (traditional media + web + platforms), moving beyond assessments that focus solely on the number of outlets. In line with the theoretical discussion reviewed, the main contribution of the INAD lies in redefining pluralism as effective pluralism of editorial decision-making centres: that is to say, it is not enough to simply note the presence of news actors; rather, it is essential to assess structural

independence, minimum standards of journalistic practice and network interdependencies (control/ownership versus collaboration).

The preliminary application in the Aysén Region illustrates the usefulness of this approach. Firstly, the regional analysis reveals an uneven distribution of media outlets: there are 63 media outlets listed, with a strong concentration in Coyhaique and Puerto Aysén, and a predominance of radio (48 stations, 76% of the total), followed by digital media (16%), TV (6%) and print media (2%). Within this framework, the analysis by municipality suggests a risk segmentation: 20% of municipalities are ‘low risk’, 20% ‘moderate risk’, 20% ‘high risk’ and 40% classifiable as ‘desert’, even where media outlets are present, precisely due to the fragility of pluralism and/or municipal dependence.

Secondly, the results show why the “hybrid” component is analytically decisive: Facebook operates as an almost universal distribution infrastructure (88.7% of actors), ahead of the web (69.4%), whilst Instagram and X are at intermediate levels (50.0% each), YouTube is used selectively (41.9%) and TikTok is in the early stages of adoption (12.9%). This pattern demonstrates that information availability can become vulnerable due to platform dependency and tendencies towards single-channel reliance in municipalities with lower media density, which complicates the equivalence between “media presence” and “robust news coverage”.

Thirdly, the transparency and accountability component (operationalised using binary variables) reinforces this assessment: whilst the most widespread indicator is Contact (~74%), followed by About (~53%) and Legal address (~48%), the criteria for assessing editorial accountability and institutional framework drop sharply (Team section/identification ~23% and Team integrity norm ~6%). In other words, a significant proportion of the ecosystem operates with visibility and contactability, but with low traceability regarding who makes editorial decisions, under what standards, and through what accountability mechanisms.

This framework is currently being tested and is expected to be further refined in line with the new features and challenges of today’s digital landscape, with the aim of examining the dynamics within sub-national media systems regarding news flows from media groups, as well as areas of collaboration to address information deserts.

However, one way to tackle the spread of disinformation in media systems is to produce comprehensive analyses, such as the INAD framework, where transparency and impartiality are fundamental to media ecosystems.

References

- Ábel, K. (2022). *How opposition-led towns in Hungary have become independent news deserts (HVG)*. Ipi.Media. <https://ipi.media/how-opposition-led-towns-in-hungary-have-become-independent-news-deserts/>
- Abernathy, Penelope Muse. (2016). *The rise of a new media baron and the emerging threat of news deserts*. Center for Innovation and Sustainability in Local Media, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. <https://www.usnewsdeserts.com/reports/rise-new-media-baron/>
- Abernathy, Penelope M. (2018). The expanding news desert. In *University of North Carolina: Center for Innovation and Sustainability in Local Media*. <https://www.usnewsdeserts.com/reports/expanding-news-desert/download-a-pdf-of-the-report/>
- Abernathy, Penelope Muse. (2020). *News Deserts and Ghost Newspapers: Will Local News Survive?* https://www.usnewsdeserts.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/2020_News_Deserts_and_Ghost_Newspapers.pdf
- Australian Competition & Consumer Commission. (2019). *Digital platforms inquiry: final report*. [https://www.accc.gov.au/system/files/Digital platforms inquiry - final report.pdf](https://www.accc.gov.au/system/files/Digital%20platforms%20inquiry%20-%20final%20report.pdf)
- Bayer, J. (2019). The illusion of pluralism: Regulatory aspects of equality in the new media. In J. Trappel (Ed.), *Digital Media Inequalities: Policies against divides, distrust and discrimination* (pp. 127–140). Nordicom.
- Cadena, C., & Zoeller, C. (2021). Periodismo en tiempos de Covid-19: Autoritarismo, Desinformación y Precariedad en América. ONU. <https://ipysvenezuela.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/Reporte-Sombra-2020-ESPAN%CC%83OL.pdf>
- Conte, A. (2022). *Death of the daily news: How citizen gatekeepers can save local journalism*. University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Damanhoury, K. E., Coppini, D., Johnson, B., & Rodriguez, G. (2022). Local News in Colorado: Comparing Journalism Quality Across Four Counties. *Journalism Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2022.2083003>
- De Moraes, D. (2011). *La cruzada de los medios en América Latina : gobiernos progresistas y políticas de comunicación*. Paidós.
- DeMendonça, T., & Brito-Batista, P. C. (2021). Local radio without borders: the experiment of a small Portuguese broadcaster on the internet. *BRAZILIAN JOURNALISM RESEARCH*, 17(2), 376–401. <https://doi.org/10.25200/BJR.v17n2.2021.1324>

- Downman, S., & Murray, R. (2020). The hyperlocal “Renaissance” in Australia and New Zealand. In *The Routledge Companion to Local Media and Journalism* (pp. 255–264). <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85102319446&partnerID=40&md5=ca4120433abf5a7dc23e27fd795fb9a1>
- Escoda, A. P., & Pedrero-Esteban, L. M. (2021). Challenges for journalism facing social networks, fake news and the distrust of z generation. *Revista Latina de Comunicacion Social*, 79, 67–85. <https://doi.org/10.4185/RLCS-2021-1519>
- FOPEA. (2021). *Desiertos informativos en Argentina*. <https://desiertosinformativos.fopea.org/>
- Freeman, J. (2020). Differentiating distance in local and hyperlocal news. *Journalism*, 21(4), 524–540. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464884919886440>
- Fundación Gabo. (2022). *La Fundación Gabo publica ‘El hormiguero’: la investigación más completa sobre medios nativos digitales latinoamericanos*.
- Fundación Gabo. (2026). *Desiertos de Noticias Locales*.
- Gulyas, Agnes. (2022). Local news deserts. In R. Matthews & D. Harte (Eds.), *Reappraising Local and Community News in the UK: Media, Practice, and Policy* (First edit, pp. 16–28). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003173144-2>
- Gulyas, A. y Baines, D. (2020). Introduction. Demarcating the field of local media and journalism. En: A. Gulyas yD. Baines (Eds.), *The Routledge Companion to Local Media and Journalism*. Routledge
- Gulyas, Agnes, Jenkins, J., & Bergstrom, A. (2023). Places and Spaces Without News: The Contested Phenomenon of News Deserts. *Media and Communication*, 11(3), 285–289. <https://www.cogitatiopress.com/mediaandcommunication/article/view/7612/3431>
- Harlow, S. (2022). A new people’s press? Understanding digital-native news sites in Latin America as alternative media. *Digital Journalism*, 10(8), 1322–1341. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2021.1907204>
- Jerónimo, P., Ramos, G., & Torre, L. (2022). *News deserts Europe 2022: Portugal Report*. https://labcomca.ubi.pt/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/news_deserts_europe_2022_.pdf
- Karlsson, M., & Rowe, E. H. (2019). Local Journalism when the Journalists Leave Town: Probing the news gap that hyperlocal media are supposed to fill. *Nordicom Review*, 40(S2), 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.2478/nor-2019-0025>
- Karppinen, K. (2013). *Rethinking media pluralism*. Fordham University Press.

- Marsden, P. (2017). *Entrepreneurial Journalism: How to go it alone and launch your dream digital project*. Routledge.
- Martín-Barbero, J. (2008). Políticas de la comunicación y la cultura: claves de la investigación. *Conferencia Del Programa de Dinámicas Interculturales de La Fundación CIDO8*
- Mellado, C, & Scherman, A. (2020). Mapping Source Diversity Across Chilean News Platforms and Mediums. *Journalism Practice*, 15(7), 974–993. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2020.1759125>
- Mesquita, L. (2023). Collaborative Journalism and Normative Journalism: Lessons from Latin American Journalism. *Anàlisi*, 68(765140), 27–44.
- Neff, T., & Pickard, V. (2021). Funding democracy: Public media and democratic health in 33 Countries. *International Journal of Press/Politics*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/19401612211060255>
- Nelson, J. L. (2021). *Imagined Audiences: How journalists perceive and pursue the public*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197542590.001.0001>
- Nygren, G., Leckner, S., & Tenor, C. (2018). Hyperlocals and Legacy Media: Media Ecologies in Transition. *NORDICOM REVIEW*, 39(1), 33–49. <https://doi.org/10.1515/nor-2017-0419>
- Owill, H. H., Chege, N., Awiti, A., & Orwa, C. (2020). Mapping Broadcast Media Outlets and Accredited Journalists in Kenya: Towards Understanding News and Information Inequalities. In *Communicatio* (Vol. 46, Issue 4). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02500167.2020.1848894>
- Polyák, G., & Urbán, A. (2024). Hungary. En S. Verza, T. Blagojev, D. Borges, J. Kermer, M. Trevisan, & U. Reviglio (Eds.), *Uncovering news deserts in Europe Risks and opportunities for local and community media in the EU* (pp. 89–96). Centre for Media Pluralism and Media Freedom. https://cmpf.eui.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CMPF_Uncovering-news-deserts-in-Europe_LM4D-final-report.pdf
- Rackaway, C. (2024). *Communicating Politics Online : Disruption and Democracy* (Second Edition). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ramos, G., Torre, L., & Jerónimo, P. (2023). No Media, No Voters? The Relationship between News Deserts and Voting Abstention. *Social Sciences*, 12(6), 345. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci12060345>

- Rodgers, S. (2018). Roots and fields: excursions through place, space, and local in hyperlocal media. *Media, Culture and Society*, 40(6), 856–874. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443717729213>
- Rodríguez-Urra, C., Trillo Domínguez, M., & Herrero Solana, V. (2024). Hyperlocal journalism in the face of the advance of news deserts: scoping re view. *Media International Australia*,0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878X241265831>
- Rodríguez-Urra C, Trillo Domínguez, M., & Herrero Solana, V. (2025). The spread of news deserts in Chile: The case of the Aysén Region. **KOME**, 13(1), 3-28. <https://doi.org/10.17646/KOME.of.20>
- Rodríguez-Urra, C. (2026). Region de Aysén Dataset (IAMCR Conference 2026) <https://zenodo.org/records/20479828>
- Salaverría, R. (2005). *Cibermedios : el impacto de internet en los medios de comunicación en España*. Comunicación Social Ediciones y Publicaciones.
- Santander, P. (2013). Leyes de medios de Chile y Argentina: tan cerca tan lejos. *Estudios Sobre El Mensaje Periodístico*, 19(2), 889–905. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_esmp.2013.v19.n2.43478
- Sapiezynska, E. (2014). Los No Aparecidos: la Protesta Social Invisible en los Grandes Medios en Chile y las Políticas Mediáticas del Disenso. *Comunicación y Medios*, 0(29), Pág. 156-170-170. <https://doi.org/10.5354/0719-1529.2014.2839>
- Sapiezynska, E., & Lagos-Lira, C. (2016). Media freedom indexes in democracies: A critical perspective through the cases of Poland and Chile. *International Journal of Communication*, 10, 549–570.
- Sepúlveda Cereceda, A. (2024). *Historia del periodismo en Chile: de la Aurora a las redes sociales*. Sudamericana.
- Smyrnaioi, N., Marty, E., & Bousquet, F. (2015). Between journalistic diversity and economic constraints: local pure players in southern France. In Rasmus Kleis Nielsen (Ed.), *Local journalism: The decline of newspapers and the rise of digital media* (pp. 165–183). I.B Tauris.
- Sousa, G. (2025). Influence of demographic, political division, and economic variables on the structure of digital news sites in Argentina. *AUSTRAL Comun.* Vol 14:.. doi: 10.26422/aucom.2025.1401.nan
- Spasov, O., Ognyanova, N., & Daskalova, N. (2024). Bulgaria. In S. Verza, T. Blagojev, D. Borges, J. Kermer, M. Trevisan, & U. Reviglio (Eds.), *Uncovering news deserts in Europe Risks and opportunities for local and community media in the EU* (pp. 22–29). Centre for Media Pluralism and Media Freedom. <https://cmpf.eui.eu/wp->

content/uploads/2024/02/CMPF_Uncovering-news-deserts-in-Europe_LM4D-final-report.pdf

- Steensen, S. (2023). Dealing With Covid-19 in Casual Democracies. *Media and Communication*, 11(3), 414–425. <https://doi.org/10.17645/MAC.V11I3.6807>
- Toomer, D. (2024). Closing the democratic deficit? Hyperlocal news sites need help to come to the rescue of socially deprived communities. In R. Matthews & G. Hodgson (Eds.), *Local journalism: Critical perspectives on the Provincial Newspapers* (pp. 46–61). Routledge
- Turner, J., & Harte, D. (2022). Where’s the fake news in hyperlocal media? Trust amongst citizen journalists and participatory audiences in local Facebook pages. In *Responsible Journalism in Conflicted Societies: Trust and Public Service Across New and Old Divides* (pp. 44–58). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003178217-5>
- Vázquez-Herrero, J., Negreira-Rey, M.-C., & López-García, X. (2023). Investigación sobre medios nativos digitales: una especialidad emergente en el campo de la comunicación digital. *Profesional de La Información*, 32(2), 1–14. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2023.mar.02>
- Verza, S., Blagojev, T., Borges, D., Kermer, J., Trevisan, M., & Reviglio, U. (2024). Uncovering news deserts in Europe Risks and opportunities for local and community media in the EU. https://cmpf.eui.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CMPF_Uncovering-news-deserts-in-Europe_LM4D-final-report.pdf
- Wang, R. Y. (2023). The Geography of Newspaper Circulations: A Spatial Taxonomy of “News(Paper) Deserts” in the United States. *Media and Communication*, 11(3), 304–317. <https://doi.org/10.17645/mac.v11i3.6856>
- Warner, M. (2019). *Funding Public Media: An Insight Into Contemporary Funding Models*. Public Media Alliance. <https://www.publicmediaalliance.org/insight-funding-public-media>